

Female to Male Sexual Harassment “Morocco as a case Study”

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ABSTRACT

Sexual harassment has proven difficult to study due to the lack of a commonly accepted definition and any standardized instrumentation that could provide comparable results across studies. Recently the focus of sexual harassment research on the harassment of women by men has been challenged. Treatments of sexual harassment of men, however, have generally ignored power differentials between the genders¹(Berdahl). According to Jennifer L. Berdahl, Vicki J. Magley, and Craig R. Waldo “Sexual harassment is rarely about sex, but about power. (Male employee, public utility company, August 1993)”².

For this reason, this study is based on two conceptual perspectives – psychoanalysis and cultural theory of female to male sexual harassment in the workplace. Selecting such approaches enables us to study the meaning of the act “sexual harassment” culturally and psychologically. We are going to review the development and evaluation of a three-dimensional model of sexual harassment (gender harassment, unwanted sexual attention in the workplace, and sexual coercion). The results of the study will work for the benefit of the current research that enriches the field of gender studies in Arab societies especially in Morocco.

Keywords:- gender harassment, unwanted sexual attention in the workplace, sexual coercion and power.

¹

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Harassment can happen anywhere, but the most common places are the workplace, street and schools. It involves unwanted and unwelcome words, deeds, actions, gestures, symbols, or behaviors that make the targeted person feel uncomfortable. Gender and sexual orientation harassment fall into this family. Involving children, "gay" or "homo" is a common insult falling into this category. The main focus of groups working against sexual harassment is protection for women, but protection for men is coming to light in recent years (Cited in Wikipedia, 2014).

I've been living [in these work quarters] for three years and I've had knocks on my door at night with guys saying, "Guess you're feeling a bit lonely, love?" It shouldn't happen. I've been sitting with a group of males and one will ask, "Don't you think it's my turn [for sex] tonight?"³

Understanding and monitoring the nature of sexual harassment is vital to developing appropriate responses and prevention strategies. Examining the nature of sexual harassment includes looking at how the sexual harassment manifests in the workplace. This includes the types and duration of harassment; who experiences sexual harassment; who the harassers are and the feature of workplaces where it happens(Clark).

This research tackles an important social issue which female to male sexual harassment in the workplace. Sexual harassment is a salient phenomenon in Morocco. Unfortunately, many people avoid talking about this social phenomenon even if it becomes part of their daily life. Many TV programs have been made about this topic. These programs were made to allow every person be aware of the issue and its bad effects on the whole society. These programs are: '**Break the silence**' (Baraka man skate), '**with no shame**' (bidon 7araj) and some other programs like '**new generation**'. Further, we can rarely find a person who has not been through that experience of harassment even once in his/her life. A research study shows that analysis predicts that behaviors identified as harassing by men stem from negotiations of gender in the workplace that challenge male dominance, whereas behaviors experienced by women as sexually harassing reinforce female subordination. Consistent with our predictions, results indicated the following: men are considerably less threatened than women are by behaviors that women have found harassing; men find sexual coercion the most threatening form of harassment; men as well as women sexually harass men; and men identify behaviors as harassing that have not been identified for women. Results also showed signs of backlash among men against organizational measures that address sexual harassment and discrimination against women. Implications for psychological and legal definitions of sexual harassment of men are discussed⁴(Berdahl). According to this analysis, the notion of sexual harassment has created a wide debate concerning the causes and effects of the act in field of gender studies.

To clarify more, there have been few studies conducted about sexual harassment in Arab Societies. The real data about the causes and effects of this phenomenon in our society is still unfound. This, in return, made it so hard for many institutions to find solutions to this daily life happening phenomenon.

Now Joseph was taken down to Egypt, and Potiphar, an officer of Pharaoh, the captain of the guard, an Egyptian, bought him from the Ishmaelites who had brought him down there. (...) Now Joseph was handsome and good-looking. And after a time his master's wife cast her eyes on Joseph and said, 'Lie with me.' But he refused (...) And although she spoke to Joseph day after day, he would not consent to lie beside her or to be with her. One day, however, when he went into the house to do

³ Australian Human Rights Commission, *Sex Discrimination Commissioner's Listening Tour – women's focus group 7* (2008).

⁴https://www.researchgate.net/publication/258181720_The_Sexual_Harassment_of_Men_Exploring_the_Concept_with_Theory_and_Data

his work, and while no one else was in the house, she caught hold of his garment, saying, ‘Lie with me!’ But he left his garment in her hand, and fled and ran outside. (Genesis, 39: 1-13)

The story of Joseph of Egypt is probably the first written account of sexual harassment (SH) in history, in which, no less, the victim is a man, and the perpetrator is a woman. The studies presented in this work concern the social perception of victims and perpetrators of SH acts depending on their gender. In this short Biblical story, Joseph becomes a victim of two types of SH: unwanted sexual attention, when Potiphar’s wife runs around the house trying to catch him and sexually abuse him, and further on we learn that there may have been an element of sexual coercion, as Potiphar’s wife punishes Joseph for not submitting to her will. We do not find the third type of SH – gender harassment with its three subtypes. But maybe Potiphar’s wife told Joseph that he should lie with her because he looks like he needs it (lewd comments); maybe she made a joke that he’s not really a man if he doesn’t want to lie with her (enforcement of gender role), or maybe she said that both Joseph and Potiphar are the same, and like all men, are good for nothing (negative gender related remarks). According to the literature on SH, all of the mentioned behaviors are examples of SH⁵(Studzńska).

So what exactly is Sexual Harassment?

Sexual harassment can be understood as a special kind of gender discrimination towards the other sex. Ironically, sexual harassment towards males is a real phenomenon, but many people disowned this fact. They found it as no more than normal comments towards males. But, comments on females and compliments are taken for granted as sexual harassment towards them. This research will present that both males and females experience the act of sexual harassment in the workplace under certain circumstances. Males harass females for fun, enjoyment and maybe for sexual intentions, females also harass rich, handsome males for the same purposes. It's far quite fair to say that the nature of sexual harassment of men disguises the gendered power issues worried in sexual harassment.

A. Research Problem

Without doubt, few research studies have been conducted on the issue of Sexual harassment towards men especially in Morocco. Thus, the main motive for selecting this topic is to provide a thorough idea about this new notion in our society. Accordingly, my aims are twofold: firstly, to help shed light on male sexual harassment in the workplace that has been ignored so many years regardless of its existence in our society, and secondly to uncover the ways used to harass men by women and to discover who is the responsible for that harassment.

My topic will tackle sexual harassment in the workplace that is practiced by females rather than males. I will bring to light the codes that the females use to harass the males, whether with their looks, walks, clothes, gaze, laughs, smiles, or even spoken starting words. All these components are sent to males to decipher it and translate it into an act, which is not always a negative act, but a well-intended one sent directly to him. This study has been made in many western nations along with the USA of America. The studies suggest that” most people of research on sexual harassment has examined the harassment of girls by means of men, reflecting the primary form of sexual harassment within the place of business [e.G., Gutek, 1985; U.S. Merit systems safety Board (USMSPB), 1981, 1987]. Surveys including the Sexual reviews Questionnaire (SEQ; Fitzgerald, Gelfand, & Drasgow, 1995; Fitzgerald & Shullman, 1985; Fitzgerald et al., 1988) had been evolved that measure the assemble of male-to-female harassment in a psychometrically sound manner, and increasing numbers of incidence research report the extent of this problem in work companies. Recently, some researchers (e.G., Popovich, Campbell, Everton, Mangan, & Godinho, 1994; Vaux, 1993) have challenged this focus and feature cautioned that the sexual harassment of male personnel may also be an crucial hassle. This challenge is reinforced by media representations of sexual harassment. For example, the recent major motion picture Disclosure (based on Michael Crichton’s bestseller) features a female executive sexually coercing a male subordinate. At the same time, increasing rates of men’s sexual-

⁵<https://tel.archives-ouvertes.fr/tel-01320713/document>

harassment grievances are given more media coverage than increasing rates of women's (e.g., Gross, 1995; Lawlor, 1994). The nature of this focus on the sexual harassment of men disguises the gendered power issues involved in sexual harassment⁶. As a result, there was a law created for such a problem in order to control this phenomenon from spreading. Many researchers tackled the idea for both men and women. According to the theory of the gaze "both men and women practice the gaze and send messages of appreciation to each other". As a result, they study each group apart, and reach out that everyone perceives and experiences sexual harassment in a different manner. Research that have attempted to study the harassment of guys (e.g., Fitzgerald et al., 1988; Gutek, 1985; USMSPB, 1981, 1987; Vaux, 1993) have forever used same measures of sexual harassment for men and women. Outcomes from some of these research indicate that the same behavioral indicators of sexual harassment have special antecedents, subjective meanings, non-public effects, and organizational effects for ladies and men (Berdahl). Even in Morocco, Sexual harassment towards women is perceived differently than sexual harassment towards men. For this reason, I am going to conduct an academic research. In general, sexual harassment falls under a broader phenomenon of negotiations of gender (e.g., Ginsburg & Tsing, 1990), that is, attempts to define and redefine what constitutes appropriate behavior and roles for men and women. Such negotiations of gender can take place both inside and outside the workplace, in the form of both sexual and nonsexual (e.g., standard discrimination) behavior. We argue that men will sense stressed via behavior that demanding situations current constructions of masculinity as a site of traits reserved for guys (e.g., dominance, privilege, and success inside the workplace), whereas ladies will sense harassed by way of conduct that boosts buildings of femininity as sub-ordination inside the administrative center.

B. Research Purpose

Sexual harassment and sexual assault are an underreported crime, which is further problematic because the European Union does not distinguish these statistics by gender. This proposal seeks to remedy the lack of statistical information about sexual assault and harassment by searching for previous incidences and collecting new data that can target unsafe public spaces in Morocco.

Women estimate that 35% of women worldwide have experienced gender violence at some point in their lives. In the Netherlands, the Ministerie van Volksgezondheid, Welzijn en Sport reports that between 200,000 and 300,000 people annually experience sexual harassment in streets and workplace. While public organizations, such as the police station, the Slachtofferwijzer, and the Juridisch Loket, receive complaints and assist women who experience gender violence (in the form of sexual assault, stalking or harassment, and domestic violence), it is known that gender violence is an under reported crime. About 60% of victims do not seek for help. Shame, fear, self-blame, and lack of trust in organizations, are some of the factors that inhibit victims from reporting gender violence and sexual harassment in the workplace. The purpose of the study is to change the common notion in Moroccan society that only males harass females. The overall objective of the study is to build a new picture on the issue based on new findings of the current time. It is hoped that this study would identify the idea that women also practice sexual harassment, but less than men do.

Furthermore, this project aims to increase reporting sexual harassment by women towards men in the workplace. It will assist victims by raising awareness of the type and location of these acts in Morocco, by creating an environment where they can report sexual harassment anonymously and easily, and by having easy to access information and resources to further assist them. It will aid policy makers by giving them additional data on how sexual harassment is practiced by women in the workplace⁷. The purpose of the study is to bring evidence to policy makers that sexual harassment in the workplace is not practiced by men only, but women play an important role in it. Ironically speaking, sexual harassment in the workplace can

⁶https://www.researchgate.net/publication/258181720_The_Sexual_Harassment_of_Men_Exploring_the_Concept_with_Theory_and_Data

⁷file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/5_metoomaastricht_mapping_sexual_harassment_in_maastricht_.pdf

happen without the intention of the other, but he /she can be part of it naturally. Being looked at, or being pointed out with the other can invite anyone to get engaged in the situation easily but both men and women are responsible of this act. To wrap up, the goal of this study is to provide a tool for men and policy makers to study sexual harassment in the workplace and create a law that goes hand in hand and saves rights for both genders (males and females) in Morocco.

C. Research Hypotheses

Drawing upon the relevant literature on female to male sexual harassment in the workplace, we hypothesize:

- **Hypothesis 1:** Though it is not a common thing, men are also subjects to sexual harassment.
- **Hypothesis 2:** men are likely to report low feeling of safety in the workplace compared to women.
- **Hypothesis 3:** men are likely to perceive a lower likelihood of sexual harassment in the workplace compared to women.
- **Hypothesis 4:** men are less experiencing sexual harassment in the workplace or semipublic place, such as in a taxi or an auto-rickshaw, compared to a public space such as waiting at a bus stop or at a roadside.
- **Hypothesis 5:** men are less likely to report higher seriousness with various types of sexual harassment relative to women.

D. Research Questions

How safe are men in the workplace? Ironically speaking, many people believe that men are safe in their workplace. What if this is not as true as we thought? How many men in the workplace are victims of gender sexual harassment?

This research will not only answer this question, but also provide resources for the sexual coercion that men suffer in the workplace. It will target female to male sexual harassment in the workplace and provide men with a voice to report and empower themselves after being victims of gender harassment.

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the following research questions will be examined:

- To what degree is sexual harassment a problem in the workplace?
- Do male and female employees have different perceptions regarding sexual harassment?
- Do men experience sexual coercion, unwanted sexual attention, and gender harassment by females in the workplace?
- What would be the most anxiety-provoking as a form of sexual harassment?
- To what extent do men report sexual harassment in the workplace as females'?

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A. Defining sexual harassment

The term “sexual harassment” emerged from North the usa inside the mid 1970s following the work of various researchers who helped carry the trouble to light (Gutek, 1985; Farley, 1978; MacKinnon, 1979). The problem that has been tricky for researchers on this area, from the very starting, is defining what constitutes sexual harassment. As with many phrases, an all-inclusive definition of sexual harassment has proved extraordinarily tough to attain. Researchers, legal scholars, and policy makers around the world have not, up to this point, agreed upon a single universal definition⁸.

One reason for this inherent trouble is that a definition could mean that boundaries might be set in this particular term which would distinguish it from different expressions of sexual interest (Gutek, 1985). As an example, sexual relationships at work aren't constantly jointly enjoyable, however they may be, additionally, now not usually sexually harassing and dangerous (Williams, Giuffre, & Dellinger, 1999). Indeed, some people argue that flirting, joking, or even sexual banter at work may be fun, as it would help to make the place of work experience less austere (Gutek, 1985; Quinn, 1977; Williams et al., 1999) (Pina).

Sexual harassment can arise in many different occasions, and may encompass however not be restrained to the following behaviors: a) the sufferer as well as the harasser may be a lady or a man. The victim does not longer must be of the alternative sex, b) the harasser can be the sufferer's manager, an agent of the organization, a supervisor in some other location, a co-employee, or a non-employee, c) the victim does not need to be the character pressured however could be anybody suffering from the offensive behavior, d) illegal sexual harassment may arise without economic damage to or discharge of the sufferer, e) the harasser's behavior must be unwelcome (EEOC, March 2008,). If any of the aforementioned behaviors takes location, then there is a case for sexual harassment consistent with US legislations (EEOC, 2008) (Pina).

Although it isn't always the case, sexual harassment is an act greater regularly perpetrated by using guys towards women (Pryor, 1995). Within the united states of america, the maximum latest statistical survey changed into conducted by means of the U.S. Advantage systems protection Board (USMSPB, 1995) surveying employees within the federal government. This survey changed into a continuation of the 2 previous USMSPB surveys (1980, 1987). The findings show that almost all (ninety three%) out of the forty four% of girls that said sexual harassment had been careworn by guys. However, sixty five% out of nineteen% of fellows that pronounced sexual harassment were burdened through women. That is to say, sexual harassment towards men starts coming to light in the last few years and in different countries.

B. History of the term sexual harassment

According to a study done by Bargad, organization for youth development in Pakistan⁹, In 1964, the usa Congress handed identify of the Civil Rights Act, prohibiting discrimination inside the place of work on the idea of race, coloration, faith, ethnicity and sex. This latter will become the criminal basis for early harassment regulation. The exercise of growing workplace pointers prohibiting harassment became pioneered in 1969, whilst the U.S. Department of protection drafted a human goals charter, setting up a policy of equal recognize for both sexes. In 1983, the Canadian Human Rights Act prohibited sexual harassment in offices below federal jurisdiction.

⁸<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222432858> An overview of the literature on sexual harassment Perpetrator theory and treatment issues

⁹ Sabiha, Shaheen. Street Harassment against Girls in District Gujranwala, Bargad, bargad.youth.organization@gmail.com

It is quite fair to have an overview over the history of sexual harassment. In fact, it helps us lot to understand the main source of it, and enables us to know the main causes that made this phrase “sexual harassment” be a common phrase in many societies and have different and difficult definitions around the world. This statement points out that the United States was the first country to be aware of this phenomenon and tries to criminalize it. A law that paves the way to both sexes to be equal in rights as they are equal in race, religion, national origin and sex. There are quite a lot to know about sexual harassment when we associate it this phrase to different cultures and behaviors. In fact, it is quite difficult to provide one definition fit and accepted everywhere. This will help us to study this notion differently even there are different definitions, behaviors, locations and purposes.

C. The Importance of Naming Sexual Harassment

The past 3 many years have seen a motion of ladies into the paid exertions Marketand developing legitimacy of the concept that women are equal, in preference to subservient, to men. The greater reputation of the idea that ladies are guys’s equals has made sexual harassment legal guidelines viable, and the existence of such legal guidelines has, in flip, further legitimized and enforced gender equality. Coined in 1975 by American feminists, the idea of “sexual harassment” assumed a worldview wherein women have been now not always uttered by sexual interest however ought to alternatively be extraordinarily irritated through it (Saguy).

Saguy suggests that the phrase”sexual harassment” was simply coined when women lead their movement of equal rights to men. They claim that what is considered or provided as a right to man, should be considered and provided to women also. So, the idea starts from the notion of being equal in everything as we are equal in duties and rights too. Women were empowered with this notion which allows them to call for different rights under the umbrella of gender equality. As a result, they claim to form a body of law that protects them against any discrimination. This notion will pave a way to some of my research questions once we go in depth in the analyses of human behaviors. Consistent with Saguy, the idea of sexual harassment has unfold throughout the globe, it still means various things in specific locations (2003, p. 2).

This remark indicates that a few think that sexual harassment is a shape of group-based totally discrimination, or as French regulation framed it as a shape of interpersonal violence. This, in return, means that the prediction about sexual harassment is incomplete across the world due to its different political and cultural dimension of each state in the world. Further, this statement answers one of the main questions of the research. The notion of sexual harassment has never had one fixed definition along history and will never have it in the future. It is a multidimensional notion that changes according to the cultural, social needs, nationally contextual, situational and depends on when, where, how the manner of sexual harassment is practiced. There are still countless debates around the world discussing different understanding of what “sexual harassment” entails and why it is wrong.

D. The Conceptual Framework of Sexual Harassment

On the grounds that the arrival of sexual harassment as a legal concept, psychology studies has tried to understand the elements that facilitate the notion of those offensive behaviors. While the legal term of sexual harassment has an ambiguous meaning and terrible connotation inside the public eye, psychology studies has conceptualized the occasions of sexual harassment as a psychological manner. Fitzgerald and co-workers (1995) evolved a conceptual model that connects the harassment criminal construction with the psychology manner and construct. Fitzgerald and colleagues (1988, 1995) proposed a three-factor structural version connecting the 2 forms of sexual harassment with 3 sex-offensive behaviors (e.G., gender harassment, undesirable sexual interest, and sexual coercion).See Appendix A for the model. These three sexually oriented behaviors originated from Till’s (1980) work that classified the experiences of college women into five types of sexual harassment: gender harassment, seductive behaviors, sexual bribery, sexual coercion, and sexual imposition. Till’s sexual harassment typology was tested through the Sexual Harassment Questionnaire (SEQ) and simplified into a three-factor structural model (Fitzgerald, et al., 1988). Eventually, this model merged into a larger theoretical framework, Integrated Model of Antecedents

and Consequences of Sexual Harassment, but remained the main measure of the three types of harassment behaviors (Fitzgerald, et al., 1997; Fitzgerald, et al., 1999).

Sexual coercion includes sexual advances, and makes the situations of employment (or schooling, for college students) contingent upon sexual cooperation.

Unwanted sexual interest also entails sexual advances, but it does not upload expert rewards or threats to pressure compliance. In this category are expressions of romantic or sexual hobby which can be unwelcome, unreciprocated, and offensive to the goal; examples encompass undesirable touching, hugging, stroking, and persistent requests for dates or sexual conduct despite discouragement, and can encompass attack (Cortina, Koss, and cook 2018; Fitzgerald, Gelfand, and Drasgow 1995; Fitzgerald, Swan, and Magley 1997).

Gender harassment is via far the most commonplace sort of sexual harassment. It refers to “a large range of verbal and nonverbal behaviors no longer aimed toward sexual cooperation however that bring insulting, opposed, and degrading attitudes approximately” contributors of 1 gender (Fitzgerald, Gelfand, and Drasgow 1995, 430). Gender harassment is in addition defined as kinds: sexist hostility and crude harassment. Examples of the sexist hostility shape of gender harassment for women encompass demeaning jokes or remarks about girls, remarks that ladies do now not belong in management positions or are not clever enough to achieve a systematic career, and sabotaging women. The crude harassment form of gender harassment is defined as using sexually crude terms that denigrate human beings primarily based on their gender (e.G., using insults including “slut” to refer to a woman coworker or “pussy” to refer to a male coworker; Fitzgerald, Gelfand, and Drasgow 1995).

Consistent with Fitzgerald’s conceptual model the 3 sorts of sexual harassment are similar but awesome (Fitzgerald et al., 1995). Gender harassment refers to the range of insulting and offensive attitudes in opposition to women. Behaviors in this category encompass however are not limited to sexual epithets, slurs, scoffs, and obscene gestures; gender-based hazing, bullying, and threats; undermining self-appreciate and performance. This kind of harassment behavior degrades the man or woman’s gender and sex position, and will be manifested as verbal, bodily, and symbolic gestures, however does now not require sexual cooperation (Fitzgerald, Swan & Magley, 1995). Gender harassment appears to be the maximum not unusual, least suggested, and maximum tolerated by means of ladies (Barak, 1995; Fitzgerald, et al., 1995). From the legal standpoint, no longer all gender harassment conditions are considered sexual harassment, but will be considered underneath the sex discrimination regulation (Fitzgerald, et al., 1995). The psychology attitude means that gender harassment provokes distress and bad have an effect on inside the victim, although it is the most subtle harassment manifestation (Parker & Griffin, 2002).

The second one type of sexual harassment, unwanted sexual interest, gives an in depth range of verbal and non-verbal behaviors that represent offensive and sex- primarily based procedures. Sexual behaviors may want to include undesirable or surprising kisses, touches, courting invites, gazing the frame; a sexual-based totally remark, remarks, jokes; sexual/homophobic graffiti, and other offensive actions. This specific harassment category will be regarded as mild harassment.

The third harassment category, sexual coercion, involves extortion of sexual cooperation in exchange for victim’s blessings or rewards (Fitzgerald, et al., 1995; Fitzgerald et al., 1995). This is the most severe, specific, and offensive class. Examples of sexual extortion may want to consist of exchange of favors for a position in a team, scholarship, starting position, or financial reward. In this category, the strength imbalance plays a vital function. Authority figures (e.G., coaches, athletic administrators, or medical personnel) call for sexual interaction in go back for the athlete’s advantage in a college or athletic software.

Studies in distinct social settings (place of job and academia) and populations seem to present comparable patterns of psychological resistance for the 3 styles of sexual harassment. Fitzgerald et al. (1988) observed that 31% of college students skilled a few shape of gender harassment, 20% stumble upon unwelcome sexual behaviors, and a pair of% skilled sexual coercion. In a go-cultural examine, Gelfand, Fitzgerald, and Drasgow (1995) compared the frequency of sexual harassment among Brazilian and American students. The observe determined comparable frequency on gender harassment (32.3% Brazilian and 34.2% Americans) and sexual coercion (three.0% Brazilian and a pair of.4% American). However, a discrepancy became discovered inside the unwanted sexual attention class, in which Brazilian (21%) record better frequency than American (11.8%), although no statistical difference become located. Scholars had been advised that girls who skilled one type of the three sexual harassment classes is probably more likely to come across the opposite harassment manifestations, mainly if the sufferer stays inside the equal social shape (Gelfand, et al., 1995; Cortina, 2001).

Sufferers of sexual harassment revel in a procedure in which sure psycho-social factors influence the direction of occasions and results. Psychology studies has discovered 3 regular variables affecting person's harassment experiences: uneven gender ratio, energy imbalance, and harassment tolerance in the organizational shape.

E. The Creation of the Concept of sexual harassment

The time period “sexual harassment” was coined via feminist activists, and their thought of sexual harassment was socio-cultural. Lin Farley claims to have determined the phenomenon of sexual harassment. The primary definitions of “sexual harassment” have been formulated by means of Farley and operating girls United. With a view to find out the pervasiveness of sexual harassment, they “distributed the first questionnaire ever committed entirely to the subject of “sexual harassment”. As Margaret puts it (2001), the definition of sexual harassment used in the survey turned into: “Any repeated and unwanted sexual comments, appears, hints or physical touch which you find objectionable or offensive and reasons you pain to your task. The perception of sexual harassment behavior is “undesirable” or “unwelcome” has characterised the concept from the beginning (Crouch 30).

It is quite fair to study why this term sexual harassment was coined and how. Most of the women suffer a lot when they refuse to have part of the situation. As a result, they were “being fired” from work, or suffering psychological problems. The survey conducted about the research gives it more importance and shed light on different practices of sexual harassment such as looks, gestures, and many other offensive behaviors. The question now is that to what extent this survey works for the best of these works? Was it beneficial enough to stop sexual harassment? Many answers and questions we will meet during the steps of this research.

F. What is Sexual Harassment?

Social scientists who've surveyed the research on sexual harassment document a huge kind of issues. These encompass troubles with definitions, sampling bias, bias inside the reviews of respondents, and researcher bias. Providing an operational definition of some concepts is very difficult because the concept is actually defined not by one behavior, but by a set of behaviors.

Operational definitions of sexual harassment are defined in terms of a set of behaviors, and *these* behaviors that are described in questionnaires. According to Margaret, a major difficulty encountered in interpreting sexual harassment research is that there is no definition upon which all researchers agree (2001, p. 31).

Sexual harassment always meets with different problems. These problems can be stated as finding too hard problems in localizing the right behavior that is considered as sexual harassment, the right sample to study, and the researcher bias. All these and more made any research on sexual harassment so hard to fully grasp. In my research, I will try to localize the category of females that practice sexual harassment as

an act. To do so, I will use operational research to some female behaviors. In short, I will study the answers of the respondents and try to sort out the right answers they provide to represent it in light of a correct and unbiased stance.

Studies suffer from problems of definition, sampling bias, respondent bias, and researcher bias. Furthermore, people continue to cite studies done in the seventies and early mid-eighties, even though awareness of sexual harassment has continued to increase, giving reason for thinking that such survey results might be out of date (Margaret, 2001, p. 106).

The subject of sexual harassment is based on a problem of which behavior to take as wrong and which one to take as normal, compliment, or unintended word. The respondents are the only key element to study this matter, I would say. Some of them may experience different situations of sexual harassment, and some may be the doers of the act. Definitions, behaviors, and situations are different, but still each one has its own version of reality.

G. Perspectives on Sexual Harassment

I have selected different kinds of definitions of sexual harassment to display. This, in return, is aimed to represent different perspectives of the phrase that are widely spread in different societies and cultures. Further, I will try to make it clear that accepting one single definition is a wrong step towards fully understand the meaning of the term and its different impacts of different societies and cultures. Through analyzing different meanings and definitions of the term, we will make it clear that the term is not applied to one group in the benefit of the other. In short, it is not as simple or innocent as some definitions represent it.

Perceptions of males and females about sexual harassment are different. Gutek and O'Connor maintain that "most of the research on the definition of sexual harassment . . . has revealed that, compared to men, women are generally more liberal, broad, and inclusive in their definition of sexual harassment"; that "almost all survey studies have found significant differences between the sexes on at least one category of behavior," but that "few surveys . . . find that men and women differ in every kind of behavior about which they are asked"; and that "some studies have not found that men and women differ." (Cited in Margaret, 2001, p.131).

The nature of the subject is problematic. After many surveys, most of them prove that the notion of harassment is not fixed within one definition. This makes defining the notion seems more complicated and so hard to grasp as a notion. Some behaviors are not considered wrong or act of harassment, some words, behaviors and acts are considered so telling about the real intention of harassment. This contradiction in framing the notion, act, behavior made the idea of sexual harassment had many branches of research and to have different perspectives.

H. A Socio-cultural Perspective

In line with MacKinnon, sexual harassment is a manifestation of the basic inequality among men and women as "guys" and "women" are constructed in our society. She argues that the very meanings of "men" and "girls" bring with them the perception that men are dominant and women are subordinate. This view is characterized by such principles as: all women are harmed by every act of sexual harassment, and women are harmed by sexual harassment in ways that similarly treated men are not. Socio-culturalists insist that an accurate understanding of sexual harassment requires a gendered analysis that takes into account the ways in which gender involves notions not just of difference but of inequality (Cited in Margaret, 2001, p. 40).

Still, the notion of sexual harassment to some people is always practiced by males against females. This notion has spread over the world for years. But, to what extent this notion is true and will still be true? Is the inequality of men and women in the society the main cause of this? There are some societies where men and women are considered equal. Thus, means that if the main cause changes do the results. In fact, sexual harassment is not only bound to this notion, it has different social and cultural effects. That is to say, sexual

harassment requires a deep analysis in each society apart. This, in return, will help to decipher its main causes and results of that social and cultural notion.

I. The Dominance Perspective

MacKinnon holds that sexual harassment is a manifestation of this gender hierarchy. It's far primarily guys who harass women. Moreover, whilst sexual harassment does generally tend to take place in institutional contexts of hierarchy, together with business enterprise/employee and trainer/scholar, it also takes location between males and females of the equal rank. For MacKinnon, that is proof of the hierarchy of gender: guys dominate women, not simply in conventional male hierarchies, however by way of virtue in their being men. MacKinnon's account gives an explanation for why sexual harassment should be conceived of as a shape of intercourse discrimination. Sexual harassment can happen handiest to ladies, in her view. What happens to men may look like sexual harassment, but because of the gender hierarchy that puts all men above all women, sexual harassment does not have the same meaning for men it has for women (Cited in Margret, 2001, p. 15).

There are several reasons to study MacKinnon's as far as she includes sex discrimination and hierarchy towards women. She tends to show that sexual harassment is a kind of rope that ties women's freedom. She was wrong when she says that all women are suffering sexual harassment, but even men experience the same thing. They just seem to have it favored. Furthermore, this is what I can call sex discrimination to favor one gender over the other. This, in return, takes us to think about the idea of bias definition, bias respondents, and bias researcher who tries to study the whole big matter from one perspective neglecting the importance of the second part. Again, this research is conducted to study the same subject, and the same stances but with an open eye to both cases.

• **Sexual harassment and Empirical research**

Empirical studies have been central to the development of our understanding of sexual harassment. Empirical research has been used to urge development of policies in workplaces and academic settings and finds its way into nearly everything written on sexual harassment as authors seek to justify their attention to the topic. Empirical data have been used to justify the claims that sexual harassment is widespread, that it happens to women much more often than it does to men, that women's perceptions of sexual conduct are different from men's, and that women who are young, divorced, nonwhite, or single are more likely to be harassed. According to Margret, these research "findings" have, in turn, shaped the concept of sexual harassment. However, many of these studies suffer from serious methodological problems, rendering their results unreliable (2001, p. 101).

Plan is of great importance to the conduct of any research that the empirical research shows in this paragraph. Empirical research helps a lot in collecting data about the causes and the real atmosphere that sexual harassment may occur. It suggests that both men and women are suffering sexual harassment, but just with different degrees. The place, the state, position in society, and also the color participating in making sexual harassment occurs as we will see later in the story of Dan and Bolen. In short, sexual harassment is always there, happening to each one, but with different ways, causes and different results with approval or refusal.

• **The philosophical concepts of sexual harassment**

In particular, philosophical conceptions of sexual harassment commonly are trying to find to articulate what it is about sexual harassment that makes the ones moves that fall beneath its purview morally wrong. Philosophical definitions of sexual harassment usually declare that sexually harassing conduct is in a few way harmful to a person. From a liberal attitude, that a form of conduct harms precise individuals is a reason for regulating that conduct. Due to the fact that we live in a liberal country, specification of this harm is crucial in justifying laws that govern sexual harassment. So, the question is, what kind of harm, if any, is as a result of sexual harassment we must save you it with the aid of the law? Philosophical conceptions of sexual harassment are trying to find to reply this question (Margaret, 2001, p. 141).

The philosophical stance is more concerned with which act is considered as sexual harassment and which one is not. This can be only measure according the harm caused by the behavior. In fact, the right question that should be added to this concept is that why not all the behaviors of interaction with others are not considered as harassment? Why some behaviors are considered as sexual harassment and other just take it as compliments or normal talk? In short, what philosophical concept is about? And why we just give the notion of sexual harassment too much attention as far as rape and abuse are not present?

• **Women harass men**

We often talk about sexual harassment against women but for this time we will be addressing the increasing problem of sexual harassment against men. In view that generations, massive numbers of ladies maintain to annoy guys silently through their provocative dressing, swinging, and publicity of their sensitive parts; the story of Joseph and Potiphar's wife in the Koran is a conventional instance of ladies sexually raiding guys, but men appear powerless to whinge.

It is known that men get stimulated by sight, while women by touch. When a woman is dressed in revealing clothes almost to nothing and walking while shaking her hips. Isn't that considered harassment?

Ms Elizabeth O. Lartey of the National Commission for Civic Education affirms this perception. She told the GNA: "Over 99 per cent of ladies, who wear skimpy provocative dress, do it intentionally. It is normally aimed at a target personality." Ms Lartey said one's target determines what, where and how to exposes it stressing "even how to pose in front of a target is a powerful weapon to confuse, harass and intimidate a man into submission". A Reverend Minister once commented: "The ladies are disturbing us with their dressing". Going further, he said; "imagine as you stand behind the pulpit and unfortunately a lady on the front row is in this provocative dress". "They sometimes intentionally or otherwise 'open up' to expose what is in between the thighs," he said. The psychological battles that men have to go through when coming across these incidents are not easy at all¹⁰.

It's far very apparent that girls face harassment extra than guys; because the EEOC numbers monitor, women are more than six instances as possibly to be sexually burdened as guys; but, the reality that girls harass men so every so often doesn't suggest that the consequences are any much less devastating for the small quantity of fellows who are the target of beside the point sexual behavior via their female bosses . We want to remember that girls may be predatory and that men may be victimized. Simply as we now renowned that boys can be raped, it's far diagnosed that men can be burdened.

• **The present studies**

The majority of studies on the perception of SH focused on other variables than the influence of the sex of the victim and perpetrator on the perception of SH. Most studies that researched how the victim and the perpetrator sex interplay in evaluation of SH showed mixed results. However, usually when the victim was female, the behavior was categorized as SH to a larger extent than when the victim was male (ex. Katz et al., 1996; Runtz & O'Donnell, 2003). Women asked to imagine themselves as victims thought they would be more anxious following SH than men imagining the same thing (Berdahl et al., 1996), and men thought they would rather be flattered by SH (Konrad & Gutek, 1986). Even fewer studies were concerned with the perception of the perpetrator. A female perpetrator harassing a man was seen as less nasty and less inappropriate than a male perpetrator harassing a woman (LaRocca & Kromrey, 1999). Harassment of a man by a female perpetrator was perceived as less serious than harassment of a man by a male perpetrator (Gordon et al., 2005). A perpetrator harassing a woman was perceived as more responsible than a perpetrator harassing a man (Valentine-French & Radtke, 1989). SH of a woman by a man was categorized as SH to a larger extent than SH of a man by a woman (Katz et al., 1996) or of a man by a man, or a man or a woman by a woman (Runtz & O'Donnell, 2003).

¹⁰<http://www.ghanaweb.com/Ghanahomepage/features/artikel.php?ID=44381>

CHAPTER 3

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

It might be difficult to conduct surveys on sexual harassment, but fortunately, many of these issues have been solved by academics. Those who want to conduct a survey on sexual harassment should adhere to the ethical standards and scientific procedures for this kind of study (WHO 2001). It is unethical to perform surveys on sexual harassment poorly since doing so could unnecessarily re-traumatize the responder. Inaccurate survey results could also be used to cast doubt on the legitimacy of a subject that is both significant and delicate (WHO 2001). However, since the 2003 survey, the Commission has conducted more research on survey methodology related to sexual harassment, and that study has revealed that new items should be added to the survey in order to improve the estimate of the occurrence of sexual harassment. This study will employ a variety of methodologies, including experimental methods, in which I will do controlled laboratory tests to determine the frequency of sexually harassing acts by females toward guys. The study will make use of questionnaires, case studies, interviews, and other qualitative methods.

In addition to collecting quantitative data from the questionnaire, I am eager to conduct interviews to acquire qualitative data regarding the actual prevalence of sexual harassment in the workplace. The interview will be used as the research method since it is very dependable and allows us to assist respondents on how to complete the questionnaires more effectively because we will be physically there with them. This strategy's drawback, though, is that it could take a lot of time.

The use of case studies in organizational research is common (Hartley 2004). Due to this, a case study will be carried out to gather information through interviews. They offer a context and process analysis that sheds light on the being researched theoretical topics. Case studies are an essential tool for comprehending the cultural and institutional background as a component in the organizational phenomenon being studied (Hartley 2004; Rousseau & Fried 2001). It is possible to conduct case studies using both quantitative and qualitative evidence (Yin 1981). I'm going to use a qualitative strategy and conduct semi-structured interviews with female workers. In order to build more in-depth knowledge about the topic, as a researcher, I will probe further with each participant.

For the aforementioned purpose, a survey questionnaire has been designed, making sure that “research questions encapsulate what the researcher is trying to find and provide the direction and shape of the research” (Hammond and Wellington, 2013, p. 127). Moreover, according to Hejase & Hejase (2013), “questionnaires are popular, low cost, and convenient (p. 187). However, Phillips & Stawarski (2008) contend that the challenge is to continuously improve the way questionnaires are worded (p. 137).

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A survey questionnaire will be created with the aforementioned objective in mind, making certain that "research questions encompass what the researcher is aiming to find and offer the direction and shape of the research" (Hammond and Wellington, 2013, p. 127). Additionally, Hejase & Hejase (2013) assert that "questionnaires are popular, affordable, and convenient (p. 187). The problem, according to Phillips & Stawarski (2008), is to consistently improve the wording of questionnaires (p. 137).

Survey forms will be another tool I use to collect data. Males and females will receive the survey form in equal numbers.

Although individual, semi-structured interviews are perhaps qualitative research's best-known methodology and might be helpful in studying sexual harassment, it also offers a wide range of other approaches (Bazeley 2003). Focus groups are another method for conducting qualitative research. They bring together people from related groups to encourage dialogue. The qualitative approach uses a critical analysis strategy while examining the law. Any novel, exhaustive, methodical, investigative, or legal examination falls under the category of qualitative research. Its goal is to examine, improve, and add value to the notion, theory, and principles. In other words, the study will use a legalistic analysis approach that places a focus on legal issues and difficulties. This study tries to fix a difficult situation by identifying the components that make up the problems and by using the content analysis technique.

Because sociolegal studies is an interdisciplinary field and incorporates all of the research techniques mentioned above, it will ultimately be undertaken (surveys, experiments, interviews, case studies,) (Banakar and Travers 2005).

A. Research Design

As previously stated, the research design would be quantitative. It will describe the issue of sexual harassment and the various perspectives that different employees have on the issue. It will examine the numerous issues raised by the study questions in an effort to learn more about the issue and how it affects the workplace. Qualitative and engaged semi-structured interviews, such as one-on-one interaction and rapport, will be used to collect precise data about sexual harassment in the workplace.

B. Sampling

In order to draw conclusions about large groups of people, researchers often look at a limited sample of the entire population. A sample is a condensed collection of items that faithfully represents the characteristics of the complete population. The investigation will focus on particular individuals from that population. All personnel in the public sector will be randomly selected to make up the research sample. I'll do research on both sexes (males and females) in the workplace, giving each group the same study questions and hypotheses. By using such a technique, the researcher can avoid prejudice.

C. Data Analysis

It is expected that when the data has been gathered, it will be entered into a computer using the SPSS 10.0 (1999) software and compiled to produce relevant information. The sample group's responses are also supposed to help with developing hypotheses.

CHAPTER 4

CONCLUSION

What appears to be most needed in this body of research is a theoretical analysis of sexual harassment that has power at its center and takes into account power differentials that exist between the genders. Such an analysis could serve as an interpretive framework for sexual harassment of both men and women, and guide future research in a constructive direction. As a beginning, the behaviors that men actually experience as sexually harassing need to be determined, and this assessment must be grounded in men's perceptions and experiences. Whether these behaviors fit psychological and legal definitions of harassment then needs to be explored.

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